

The Analysis of Sinop Battle (1853) in Terms of Management Functions.

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Abstract

Commander performs management functions by the means of possessing management and leadership features; it has been said that a commander succeeds orders which are given during peacetime with the help of planning, staffing, coordination and management functions. Commander has to manage leadership functions, give direction, create common purpose and motivate in order to cope with changes in the environment. In this paper, The Sinop Battle which took place between the Ottoman Empire and Russia in 1853, were examined in terms of strategic and tactical reasons management functions.

Key Words: Organization, Management, Leadership, Strategic Leadership.

1. Introduction

The environments in which the organization evolves the employees who have to change their work. In this context, the leader's mission is to make sure if it is in harmony with the environment. Leaders, preparing for the future organization, should have the necessary equipment. One of the most important issues is that leaders must convince employees that they can accomplish their work.

Changes taking place in the world has led to the phenomenon of change. Problems of management and leadership style to detect, manage, and resolve requires serious changes. Therefore, people who will make a difference and excellence have become an important element of leadership.

Leadership nowadays are not limited to mobilization and affect people processes. Humanity's current knowledge, skills, abilities change the phenomenon of "thought the person who created" for leaders and of "business person who" for followers. The past simple leader- follower relations are more complicated than it has become because intensified competition and the ability to take advantage of the most valuable resources are very valuable in today's society.

Commander of the combat should integrate direction, motivate and make collection under a common purpose in order to cope with changes by master leadership functions.

a. Commander's intent in the volatile environment and intention to determine strategy,

b. During the occupation, Atatürk's lyrics "As they have come, so they will go." and in the war of independence "there is no line defense there is zonal defense"; after the great offensive "armies, your first target is Mediterranean sea. Go ahead", indicates the strong personality and exemplary behavior.

Manager captures the danger and the possibility

of errors while leader

pursue opportunities that will arise even in times of danger.

The manager is dealing with how to formulate and develop it Leader, on the other hand leader is concerned with the immediate implementation of the current strategy and the creation of culture. In this context;

Instead of producing strategy, Mustafa Kemal actually start the war with the help of Amasya Circular letter by going forth from Samsun to Anatolian

The manager's mind is busy with danger and the possibility of errors; The heart of a leader endeavor to seize opportunities and to improve the success multiply.

As an Ottoman Pasha, Mustafa Kemal deployed to quell the rebellion in the region by publishing the Amasya Circular in this case he demonstrated grand leadership qualities and, Amasya Circular was used as an opportunity for the initiation of the War of Independence.

The manager is in effect at the establishment of the authority and importance of the chain of command. On the other hand, the purpose of the organization leaders is to give weight to the elements that affects the direction for followers.

While Atatürk had reputation with its powers and its power to ensure removal of the reign, he preferred to first convince his close friends and colleagues to reach a wide audience.

2. The functions of Management

Commander performs management functions management by using leadership as features (John Kotter, 1999). It has been said that a commander succeeds orders which are given during peacetime with

the help of planning, staffing, coordination and management functions. However, management functions, listed, will be inadequate to fulfill orders in combat conditions (John Kotter, 1999). Commander has to manage leadership functions, give direction, create common purpose and motivate in order to cope with changes in the environment.

a. Planning and Direct:

The main way to deal with the mess is detailed planning. In line with the strategic objectives, various periods (daily, weekly, monthly or annual) targets are defined. Then, step by step how to perform these objectives are described in detail and the necessary resources are allocated for each step. However, the planning is not only a way of dealing with changes. After completed, planning will begin to shape. Planning explain definitions for achieving a particular outcome. If the result to be achieved will be change, then the plan will be outdated.

For this, the commander of the change in the environment, primarily intense environment; firstly should show intention and the final result to be achieved, and then direct how to perform this intention in order to determine the strategy. In summary, commander's intent and its strategy that intends to perform, is a leadership function; on the other hand planning activities without losing their way in this direction to ensure progress is a management function.

b. Assignment and Creating Common Purpose:

Meeting the requirements of the assignment of tasks and based on this giving orders are the basic management functions that a commander must fulfill. Corresponding to these activities, the leadership function is gathering people under a common purpose (John Kotter, 1999). Leader utilize this function by explaining the goal to his subordinates and allowing them to adopt this goal is realized (Michelle Watson, 2002). The leadership function will be come out when it comes to the stage to be greeted by the event. If you notice, "design", "model building" activities are being orders while collecting under the common goal requires intense communication (R.Conger, 1991). Commander makes subordinates understand the aim thanks to intensive communication.

In short giving them clear instructions and giving orders will not guarantee successful results. Changing circumstances may void given the assignment instructions. In such cases, if unit commander was able to collect subordinates under a common purpose, then the subordinates avoid falling to despair.

c. Coordination / Control and Motivation

Director realizes the execution of the plan by using mechanisms of coordination and control. For this reason, compares plan with the results obtained. This will be completed with the inspection and meeting tools. Later deviations from the plan are found to identify solutions to problems. Leader makes coordination to prevent recurrence of the problem (Abraham Zaleznik, 1999).

Leaders inspire and motivate subordinates to create the common goal (John Kotter, 1999). Despite the changes and obstacles in the specified direction, provides the same vigor progress by appealing to people's sense of values (J.Burns, 1978).

3. The Sinop Battle

On 30 November 1853 Ottoman Navy was raid and being completely destroyed by the Russian Navy in the Black Sea port of Sinop. Navy Commander Admiral Nakhimov, just before the raid, gathered the crew and made the following speech;

I'll tell you my idea about the first instructions put commander in a difficult situation in the changing the status. So I, as you all detached, would allow you to move the way you want, but instead I want you to do your duty. Because the emperor and ruler of Russia, the Black Sea fleet await the glorious heroism. Expected to justify depends on us. "

In this case the Navy's Commander displayed not only get familiar with subordinates but also express his faith in them and highlight their expertise to motivate them to success. In addition, he have used devolution, enabled them to gain freedom of movement and demonstrated a flexible approach to strategic leadership.

During the Sinop Battle the number of Ottoman navy was greater than the number of the Russian navy. However, the Russian armored ships and guns more powerful and longer range and have the opportunity to lay roses were filled with gun powder. Such a force imbalance, the Ottoman navy lost the war before it starts Raid was inevitable after the fleet remained in Sinop.

I. Strategic Fault; Ottoman Navy Captain Osman Pasha could not analyze internal and external factors and could not perform deployment to gain tactical advantage. He could not benefit from opponent's weaknesses and environmental conditions.

II. Tactical Fault: Any other ship was not commissioned for the protection of Sinop ships waiting at anchor .This is a requirement of naval

warfare tactics, though it is ignored by Navy Captain. In this respect, one of the ship commander Mr. Ali made warnings but they were not taken into account.

4. Conclusion:

a. Stronger Russian ships and armored guns had a longer range. Despite this imbalance of power and oppression, the fleet remained in Sinop, and so the inevitable defeat came out.

b. Internal and external threats were not analyzed, tactical advantages were not located properly, and the warning made by the ship commander was not also taken into account,

c. Navy personnel were uneducated, unmotivated and they have not been encouraged and so that the increase loss.

5. Analysis:

The analysis of Sinop Battle in terms of management functions with respect to strategic and tactical reasons;

a. Planning / Guidance

I. Threats and Environmental Conditions have not analyzed, the A-B-C Plan does not exist, be shortsighted and lack of timely decisions,

II. Effective and competent leadership not displayed (Knowledge-Skill-Effectiveness inadequate),

III. Lack of freedom for Flexible Environment,

IV. Devolution of powers not given to personnel.

b. Creating Common Purpose

I. Communication and lack of coordination (consultation),

II. Team work is not available,

III. Distrust of Staff,

IV. Lack of deploying credential,

V. Uneducated Staff.

c. Motivation

I. Initiative not given to Staff,

II. Not being encouraged,

III. Success disbelief.

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